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Effect Of Bank Capital Reforms On Private Sector Investment In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of bank capital reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. for the period of 1987 to 2021. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of total bank capital based and total asset based on private sector investment. The variables were private sector investment as the dependent variables while total bank capital based and total asset based, were the independent variables. These variables were sourced from the central bank of Nigeria bulletin. The population of the study was deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited, The Autoregressive Distributive Lag approach was employed for the analysis The study found that, total bank capital based has positive significant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria, total asset based has positive significant effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. The study concludes that bank capital reforms have contributed positively to investment expansion by improving the stability, efficiency, and lending capacity of the banking sector. The study recommended Regulatory authorities, particularly the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), should continue to enforce and periodically review capital adequacy requirements to ensure banks remain resilient and capable of supporting private sector investment. Banks should be encouraged to channel asset growth towards productive sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing, agriculture, and SMEs, to maximize the investment-enhancing effects of increased asset bases.

Keywords: total bank capital based, total asset based, bank capital reforms, private sector investment

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a central role in the economic development of any nation by mobilizing savings and channeling funds to productive investment activities. In Nigeria, the banking industry constitutes the backbone of financial intermediation, given the limited depth of the capital market and the heavy dependence of the private sector on bank credit for investment financing. Consequently, reforms aimed at strengthening the capital base of banks have attracted sustained policy attention, particularly in relation to their implications for private sector investment and overall economic growth (Wike, Nwonodi, & Okocha, 2025). Bank capital reform refers to regulatory and policy measures designed to enhance the capital adequacy, resilience, and operational capacity of deposit money banks. In Nigeria, such reforms have

been motivated by recurring episodes of bank distress, weak capitalization, poor corporate governance, and inadequate risk management practices that historically undermined the stability of the financial system (Ogbuagu Akidi Oladosu & Enyinnaya, 2024). These weaknesses constrained banks' ability to provide long-term credit to the private sector, thereby limiting investment, employment creation, and industrial expansion. One of the most significant banking reforms in Nigeria occurred in 2004–2005, when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) raised the minimum capital requirement for commercial banks from ₦2 billion to ₦25 billion. This reform led to consolidation through mergers and acquisitions, reducing the number of banks while strengthening their balance sheets. Subsequent reforms, including post-global financial crisis regulations and recent recapitalization directives, have continued to emphasize capital adequacy as a means of promoting financial stability and enhancing banks' capacity to finance economic activities (Ele, & Okwajie, 2025).

Private sector investment is widely recognized as a key driver of economic growth, productivity improvement, and structural transformation. In Nigeria, the private sector encompasses manufacturing, agriculture, services, trade, and small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs), all of which rely heavily on external financing (Habiba Miftahu & Abdulazeez 2025). However, access to finance has remained a major constraint to private investment due to high interest rates, short loan tenors, credit rationing, and risk aversion by banks. These challenges raise critical questions about whether bank capital reforms have translated into increased credit availability and improved investment outcomes for the private sector (Olayemi, Okonji, & Ogbeiwi, 2021).

Theoretically, well-capitalized banks are expected to have greater lending capacity, enhanced risk-bearing ability, and improved confidence among depositors and investors. Strong capital positions enable banks to absorb shocks, comply with prudential regulations, and extend credit to productive but riskier sectors of the economy (Ndukwe, & Allison, 2021). From this perspective, bank capital reform should stimulate private sector investment by improving the quantity, quality, and stability of bank lending. However, empirical evidence from Nigeria remains mixed, as some studies suggest that banks may channel increased capital toward government securities and non-productive assets rather than private sector lending.

In recent years, Nigeria's economy has faced macroeconomic challenges such as economic recessions, exchange rate volatility, inflationary pressures, and declining oil revenues. These conditions have heightened the need for a vibrant private sector capable of driving diversification and sustainable growth. Against this backdrop, understanding the extent to which bank capital reforms influence private sector investment becomes increasingly important for policymakers, regulators, investors, and development practitioners. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the relationship between bank capital reform and private sector investment in Nigeria. By analyzing how changes in bank capitalization affect credit allocation and investment behavior in the private sector,

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite several bank capital reforms implemented in Nigeria to strengthen the financial system, private sector investment has remained relatively low and volatile. The Nigerian economy is largely bank-dependent, and the private sector relies heavily on deposit money banks for investment financing due to the underdevelopment of alternative funding sources such as the capital market and venture financing. However, access to adequate, affordable, and long-term credit by private enterprises continues to be a major challenge, raising concerns about the effectiveness of bank capital reforms in stimulating private sector investment. Over the years, the Central Bank of Nigeria has introduced various capital reform measures, including increased minimum capital requirements, bank consolidation, recapitalization exercises, and stricter prudential regulations. These reforms were primarily designed to enhance banks' capital adequacy, stability, and lending capacity. In theory, well-capitalized banks should be better positioned to extend credit to the private sector, absorb financial risks, and support productive investment activities. In practice, however, evidence suggests that many Nigerian banks remain risk-averse, preferring to allocate funds to government securities and short-term trading activities rather than

financing long-term private sector investments, particularly in manufacturing and small and medium-scale enterprises.

Furthermore, private sector investment in Nigeria has been constrained by high lending interest rates, short loan maturities, stringent collateral requirements, and weak credit appraisal mechanisms. These constraints persist despite improvements in bank capitalization, suggesting a possible disconnect between bank capital reforms and real sector financing. This situation raises critical questions about whether bank capital reforms have effectively translated into increased credit availability and enhanced investment outcomes for the private sector. Additionally, macroeconomic instability, characterized by inflation, exchange rate volatility, and periodic economic recessions, has further weakened banks' willingness to lend to the private sector. In some cases, higher capital requirements may have unintentionally encouraged banks to focus on balance sheet strengthening and regulatory compliance at the expense of private sector lending. As a result, the expected positive impact of bank capital reforms on private sector investment may not have been fully realized. Empirical studies on bank capital reform and private sector investment in Nigeria have produced mixed and inconclusive results. While some studies report a positive relationship between bank capitalization and private sector credit growth, others find insignificant or even negative effects. These inconsistencies may be attributed to differences in data periods, methodological approaches, or failure to account for structural and macroeconomic factors. Consequently, there remains a gap in empirical evidence regarding the actual impact of bank capital reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. In light of these challenges, the central problem this study seeks to address is whether bank capital reforms in Nigeria have significantly improved private sector investment, and to what extent enhanced bank capitalization has translated into increased and sustained financing of private economic activities. Addressing this problem is crucial for designing effective banking policies that can promote private sector-led growth, economic diversification, and sustainable development in Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of bank capital reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

6. Assess the effect of total bank capital based on private sector investment in Nigeria;
7. Examined the effect of total asset based on private sector investment in Nigeria;

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Bank Capital Reforms

Banking sector reforms emphasizes the notions of bank capitalization through consolidation. The fulcrum of bank capitalization is setting the capital base upon which a player can set up and be licensed to operate banking functions (Jegade, 2014). Ajayi (2005), states that a bank with a strong capital base has the ability to absolve losses arising from non performing liabilities (NPL). There are, of course, some grounds to question the primacy often ascribed to capital among the factors driving the solvency of banks. For instance, Sanusi (2012) argued that, "high capitalization does not automatically translate to improved bank risk management". In the process of tackling banking problems through capital infusion, the relevant issue is not the level of capital injected into a bank but rather, the optimality of the investment portfolio mix generated from the expanded capital base.

2.1.2 Private Sector Investment

In Keynesian terminology, investment refers to addition to capital equipment which enables an increase in the production of capital goods (Jhingan, 2002). The term, investment, according to Ibenta (2005), may be defined as accumulation and commitment of fund in financial and real assets with the objective of obtaining income over time. He further noted that it is a commitment of resources made in the hope of realising benefits that are expected to occur over a reasonably long period of time in the future. Investment can also be referred to as the production of capital goods (Heim, 2008). Investment thus includes new plant and equipment, construction of public works like roads, dams, buildings, etc. Investment can be defined as the outlay of money for future use (Agu, 2015).

Investment can be made by the corporate organisation for individual stakeholders or directly by the individual in a certain project. This is known as Private Investment. But, when the commitment of funds for productive purposes is done by the government for the betterment of the citizenry, it is called Public Investment. Private sector investment in Nigeria is faced with some daunting challenges. For decades, Nigeria's economy was characterized by growing dominance of the public sector over the private sector. The private sector faced numerous problems which include; the poor state of physical infrastructure, particularly road networks, electricity and water supply; inadequate credit to the private sector, which has done-tailed to high cost of production; insecurity in the country; corruption at various levels; weak institutions, etc. (Okorie&Chikwendu, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this research is anchored on the theoretical arguments of both classical and neoclassical postulations as mirrored in the seminal work and empirical studies carried out by Schumpeter (1911) and Mckinnon (1973), and Shaw (1973). These distinguished scholars have consistently maintained throughout their arguments that financial development has a strong correlation with growth through investment. They maintain that under the assumption of a well-functioning and result driven market, financial liberalization tremendously enhances efficiency in resource allocation and promotion of competition which greatly results in competitive prices for goods and services.

Indeed, Ronald Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) consolidating on the foundation solidly laid by the seminal work of Schumpeter (1911) propound the financial liberalization theory which they strongly argue that government restrictions on the banking Sector greatly restrain both the quantity and quality of investment. Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) no doubt, are the first to expound the notion of financial liberalisation. Theoretically, an economy with an efficient financial system can easily achieve growth and development through functional and efficient capital allocation. Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) argue that historically, many countries including advanced economies but more especially developing ones have restricted competition in the financial sector as a result of government interventions and controls of the monetary policy of the banks.

Strictly based on their argument, a repressed financial sector discourages both savings and investments since the rate of return is very much lower than what can ordinarily be obtained in a competitive market. In a situation like this, the financial intermediaries cannot function at their full capacity since they are tremendously inhibited from efficient channeling of savings into productive investment which greatly hinders the development of the overall economic system.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okoi, Ocheni and Orok (2019) examined the impact of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data for forty six years spanning from 1970 to 2015. The study captured bank reforms as interest rate spread, exchange rate, bank capital base, and corporate governance disclosure index. The data were analyzed using Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) test. The results found that interest rate spread was correctly signed and adequately predictive of economic growth indicator studied while other exogenous variables did not impact positively on gross domestic product growth in Nigeria. Further result indicated existence of a long-run relationship among these variables and short run adjustment effects.

Nteegah, Udeorah and Owede (2017) investigated the effect of banking sector consolidation- credit allocation to selected sectors on the growth of Nigerian economy. The study employed time series data on growth rate of GDP, banking sector credit distribution to the agriculture, manufacturing, oil and gas/mining, commercial (export financing) sectors and bank size (number of Deposit money bank branches) for the period 1981 – 2015. The data were analyzed using Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The results showed that only the banking sector credit allocation to the manufacturing sector had positive and significant effect; banking credit to agriculture, oil & gas/mining, commercial (export financing sectors) and bank size were all insignificant.

Nkemakolam (2017) investigated the effect of bank capital reforms on economic growth of Nigeria between 1986 and 2013. The study proxied capital reform using total bank capital and total bank reserve

while economic growth was captured as Gross Domestic Product. The Johansen co-integration approach was employed for data analysis. The results showed that bank total capital and bank reserve have positive and significant effects on GDP. This indicates that bank reforms have a long run significant positive effect on economic growth of Nigeria.

Akpansung and Gidigbi (2014) employed the OLS regression technique to investigate the relationships between banking reforms and credit allocations to sectors and aggregate output in Nigeria. The results showed that banking reforms have positive and significant effect on the credit allocated to the activity sectors (agriculture, mining & quarrying, manufacturing, communication, and oil and gas). The study further revealed that credit allocation to mining & quarrying and oil & gas sector significantly increases economic growth by 52.4% for the period under study. Furthermore, a unit increases in credit allocated to the oil & gas subsector increase economic growth 30.6%.

Akinkoye and Oyelami (2014) investigated the relationship between bank recapitalization and performance of the real sector. The structural break test conducted on the estimated OLS regression line in the study shows that bank recapitalization policy resulted in a significant difference in the output of the real sector in the period before and after the recapitalization of banks. The outcome showed that increased capital base of banks is a boost to the output of the real sector in Nigeria.

Ishiorore (2017) investigated the banking sector reforms and economic growth using time series data from 1970 to 2013 for the Nigerian economy. Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) Bounds test was applied for the specific determination of the long and short-run relationships between banking sector reforms and economic growth. The research finds that the interest rate margin is more significant than other variables in the model in explaining the banking sector reforms and economic growth. Banking sector credit to the private sector was negative and statistically insignificant on economic growth in Nigeria. The study posits that capital reforms does not enhance economic growth.

Lotto (2018) examined the impact of capital requirements' regulation on bank operating efficiency in Tanzania. The study employs bank level data for the period between 2009 and 2015. The findings show a positive and significant relationship between capital ratio and bank operating efficiency. This result may also imply that the increased regulations on capital requirements influence the bank's decision to revisit their internal operations strategy in terms of strong corporate governance, risk assessment methods, credit evaluation procedures, employment of more qualified staffs, and enhanced internal control procedures. Another key finding is an inverse relationship between non-performing Loans (credit risk) and bank operating efficiency..

Oyetayo, Osinubi and Amaghionyediwe (2019) investigated the effect of capital adequacy on bank performance in Nigeria. Primary based secondary data from selected banks was used for the study. Unit Root Test and Pooled Panel Least Squares Estimation as well as the Breuch Godfrey rest were carried out in the study. The study's findings, among others, showed that capital adequacy had a positive and significant effect on the banks' performance while liquidity has a negative and significant relationship with the performance of the selected banks.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in this study. This design is suitable for secondary data studies, especially when the data has already been documented and authenticated by some great research based institutions like the World Bank, IMF, CBN among others (Kerlinger, 1973). It is a well-known fact that in this regression study, the researcher investigated a cause and effect relationship without manipulating the existing data.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data which are collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria publications. The data covered a period of thirty five (35) years (1987 to 2021). This period covered the post Structural Adjustment Programme era.

3.3 Model Specification

The model is premised on the assumption that bank capital reform can influence private sector investment. This supposes that model 1 below holds for the banks in Nigeria.

$$PI = f(TBC, TA) \text{ -----Model 1}$$

Where:

PI = private sector investment

F= Functional notation

TBC = Total Bank capital base representing bank reforms

TA = Total asset base to capture the bank size

This can be rewritten in equation form as follows:

$$PI = a_0 + a_1TBC + a_2TA + \mu \text{ -----Eqn 2}$$

a_0 is the autonomous value of the constant while a_{1-2} are the coefficients of the independent variables. The μ is the error term that smoothes the stochastic effect of time series disturbances on the model.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

This study adopt econometric techniques in testing the effect of bank capital reforms on private sector investment. It employs time series data necessitates stationarity tests in order to avoid spurious results. The unit root test is expected to determine the nature of the time series data and the most suitable tool of regression technique to employ. It is expected that in cases where all the variables are stationary at level (1(0)), the Ordinary Least Square tends to be the most suitable regression technique, whereas the Johansson cointegration works better in situation where all the variables take the forms of first order integration 1(1). In cases where the econometric variables have a combination of both level 1(0) and first integration 1(1), the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) works best.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests was employed to determine the stationarity or otherwise of variables used in the study. The ADF tests are done on level series, and first order difference series. The decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, otherwise, accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value.

Table 1: Summary of Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Variables	At Level	1(0)	At First Difference		Order of Integration
	T-stat	P.Value	1(1)		
	T-stat	P.Value	T-stat	P.value	
Private Sector Investment (PI)	-3.929579	0.0056	-	-	1(0)
Total Bank capital base (TBC)	-1.329579	0.5656	-3.329579	0.0256	1(1)
Total asset base (TA)	-2.429271	0.0756	-6.108636	0.0000	1(1)

The stationarity test otherwise called unit root analysis shows that some of the variables are stationary at level {that is had no unit root at 1(0)} while others were not stationary at level but become stationary in their first differences {that is, they had no unit roots at 1(1)}.

The variables with the order of integration of 1(0) is Private Sector Investment Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value at level, thus we rejected the null hypothesis as the p.values are less then 0,05 and conclude that each of them is stationary at level 1(0).

Those that have the order of integration of 1(1) are TBC, TA, Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value, the p.values of the ADF of each of these variables is greater than the 5% critical value at level but less than 0.05 at their first difference. Therefore, all the variables are all stationary at either level 1(0) or first difference 1(1). The stationarity is used to determine the most suitable regression techniques for the model developed for the study.

4.2 Estimation of Long run Effect of Bank Capital Reforms on Private Sector Investment

The test of cointegration for the presence of a long-run relationship in the models is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: ARDL Bounds Test for long run effect of bank reforms on private sector investment

Models	F-Statistic	Lower Critical Value Bound at 5% level	Upper Critical Value Bound at 5% level
Bank Capital Reforms	38.7432*	2.45	3.61

*significant at 5%

From the results in Table 2, the critical bound values were computed at 5% level of significance. The lower critical bound value is 2.45 while the upper critical value is 3.61. The F-statistics for models are 38.7432. The F-statistics for the models are greater than the Upper (3.61) and Lower (2.45) critical bound values. Thus we rejected the null hypotheses for the models and conclude presence of long run relationship in all the models.

4.3 Analyses of ARDL Long Run Coefficients and Error Correction

Having established the presence of long-run relationships in banking capital reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria, this section explained the nature of the relationship as well as the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. The results from CointEq (-1) from the cointegrating form is used to explain the speed of adjustment. The nature of the relationship is explained by the long run coefficients.

4.3.1 Analyses of Long Run Effects of Bank Capital Reforms on Private Sector Investment

Table 3: Model of the long Run relationship between bank capital reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PI(-1))	1.039810	0.277245	3.750509	0.0331
D(TBC)	0.002621	0.001024	2.560316	0.0832
D(TBCL(-1))	-0.004492	0.001097	-4.094364	0.0263
D(TBC(-2))	0.002671	0.001934	1.380650	0.2613
D(TA)	0.010966	0.003202	3.424595	0.0417
D(TA(-1))	-0.006046	0.002548	-2.372973	0.0982
D(TA(-2))	-0.006007	0.001941	-3.094517	0.0535
CointEq(-1)	-0.100379	0.184168	-0.545042	0.6236

Cointeq = PI - (0.0402*TBC + 0.3049*TA -10.4583)

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TBC	0.040218	0.068843	0.584199	0.6001
TA	0.304891	0.579615	0.526022	0.6353
C	-10.458289	17.339872	-0.603135	0.5890

Analysis of the nature and significance of the relationship between bank capital reform and private sector investment is shown on Table 3. From the results, the error correction of -0.1004 at a probability value of 0.6236 is shown. The coefficient has a negative sign suggesting the possibility of a return on long run equilibrium. However, since the p.value is greater than 0.05, it indicates an insignificant speed of adjustment. This suggests that bank capital base reforms does not have a significant long-run policy effect

on the private sector investment in Nigeria. This implies that bank capital reform has not played instrumental roles in driving private sector investment in Nigeria. The long-run coefficients of regression confirmed the insignificant long-run effects since all the bank capital reform variables (TBC, TA) have p.values that are greater than 0.05.

4.3.2 Short run Effect of Bank Capital Reform on Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Bank Capital Reform and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PI(-1)	0.795661	0.501634	1.586139	0.2109
PI(-2)	1.655111	1.630442	1.015130	0.3848
PI(-3)	-1.915205	1.260089	-1.519897	0.2259
TBC	0.761345	0.447073	1.702957	0.1871
TBC(-1)	1.554731	1.268706	1.225446	0.3078
TBC(-2)	2.723949	0.412514	6.603283	0.0071
TA	7.196438	1.972018	3.649275	0.0355
TA(-1)	7.650823	3.589890	2.131214	0.1229
TA(-2)	6.827734	1.777909	3.840316	0.0311
TA(-3)	7.051449	2.421617	2.911877	0.0619
C	-971.9103	341.9209	-2.842500	0.0655
R-squared	0.999944			
Adjusted R-squared	0.999461			
F-statistic	2067.766			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000015			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.676546			

The ARDL result of the short-run effect of bank capital base reform on private sector investment in Nigeria is presented in Table 4. The coefficient regression of the dependent variable (Private Sector Investment) showed positive effects at first and second years, but negative effect in the third year. However, the p.values are all greater than ($p > 0.05$) 0.05 level of significance. This supposes that private sector investment is not an endogenous factor in the model.

Table 4 further revealed that the Total Bank Capital (TBC) has a positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods from level to 2 years. However, only the lag 2 coefficient of TBC had significant relationship with PI in Nigeria. This supposes that a unit increase in TBC by the bank management will bring about 2.72 units of rise in the private sector investment in Nigeria.

Similarly, the Bank Total Asset (TA) showed positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods within the short-term frame spanning at level 0(1)to lag 3. Nonetheless, the p.values indicates significant relationships at level, and lag 2. This indicates that a unit increase in TA leads to 7.19 and 6.82 units of increase in PI at level and Lag 2 respectively.

On the overall, the adjusted coefficient of determination ($Adj R^2$) revealed that about 99% of the change in the private sector investment can be explained by bank capital base reform in Nigeria. This is confirmed by a significantly significant p.value of 0.000 from the F-statistics (2067.766). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.67 suggests a suspicion on the confounding influence of trends on the reliability of the model.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings was done in line with the objectives of the study.

Effect of Bank Capital Reform on Private Sector Investment

Bank capital reforms have a 99% significant short run policy effect but no significant long run effects on private sector investment in Nigeria. The result means that bank capital standing has no long run effect on the ability of the banks to finance and boost private investment in Nigeria. It is the level of capital base and management consciousness with strategic plans that determine how much to lend out and interest for boosting investments in the private sector. Extant literature supposes that private sector lending is a very risky asset exposure and hence demands care and strategic management policies. Be that as it may, capital base is prime determinant of private sector investment profile in Nigeria. Further analysis revealed that total bank capital (2.7239, $p = 0.0071$) and total assets (7.1964, $p=0.0355$) influence private investment positively. This supposes that bank capital and assets are drivers for short run growth in private sector investment in Nigeria.

Both the a priori and theoretical postulation are that capital base increases the propensity of the bank to withstand financial shocks on assets and incidences of long term loans. This implies that bank capital base has positive relationship with economic prospects and private investment. This agrees with previous studies of Okoi, *et al* (2019), Nkemakolam (2017), Akpansung and Gidigbi (2014), and Akinkoye and Oyelami (2014). These studies support the fact that bank capital reforms impact positively on growth and other attendant indices of growth such as investment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the effect of bank capital reforms on private sector investment, using total bank capital base and total assets base as key explanatory variables. The empirical findings reveal that both variables are statistically significant, indicating that bank capital reforms have played an important role in enhancing private sector investment. The increase in banks' capital base has strengthened their capacity to absorb risks, improve credit creation, and enhance financial intermediation. Similarly, the growth in total assets base reflects improved balance sheet strength, enabling banks to extend more long-term and investment-oriented financing to the private sector. Overall, the results suggest that bank capital reforms have contributed positively to investment expansion by improving the stability, efficiency, and lending capacity of the banking sector. The study recommend that Regulatory authorities, particularly the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), should continue to enforce and periodically review capital adequacy requirements to ensure banks remain resilient and capable of supporting private sector investment. Banks should be encouraged to channel asset growth towards productive sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing, agriculture, and SMEs, to maximize the investment-enhancing effects of increased asset bases. Policymakers should support the development of long-term funding instruments and incentives that enable banks to leverage their stronger capital and asset bases in financing long-term private sector investments.

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